

Automated theorem proving: On how computers and DNA molecules can do mathematical proofs.

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1 Introduction

Hello mathsfans!¹. As you may know, mathematicians discover new facts every day, and every fact they find needs to be proven in order to ensure it's not just true, but valid. The thing is, mathematicians' purpose is basically the ability to do proofs, that's why they still exist, because of their power of abstraction that's really really hard to emulate. This means that, if we could emulate completely the mathematical human thought and the abstraction power in order to “teach” machines how to do proofs, mathematicians would have basically no reason to exist. Ironically, mathematicians have developed the theory required to teach computers how to do proofs, at least very basic proofs, however, even if it's not enough power to make mathematicians disappear –yet–, it provides a pretty useful tool to verify some reasonings are valid and, when they're pretty easy to do –but long and tedious–, using an automatic theorem prover might be pretty useful. In this essay, we'll explore some of the most basic techniques to do automatic theorem proving and at the end, a pretty interesting relation between the DNA, computation and, automated proofs. Not just that, you'll learn how to do a simple automatic theorem prover! So get your coding and math skills ready to explore this new journey.

2 What's mathematical logic about?

The way mathematicians generate new knowledge is: by starting from a set of initial truths and applying some rules that ensure we get to some final truths. The steps mathematicians take in order to ensure the knowledge generated is valid, they created mathematical logic, whose tools allow us to formalize the reasoning we do in mathematics in an algorithmic way, and this is also why computers can run these processes. Before moving to the computational part where we talk about machines proving statements to follow from others, we need to have a solid understanding of these concepts, starting from inference rules.

¹In the case i win, i need to greet all the readers in a familiar way of course!

2.1 Inference rules: the reason why we can do proofs

Reasoning can be defined as a process where, starting from a set of statements called hypotheses, or premises, we get to a conclusion (thesis). Now, how's this set of premises? Well, we're finite creatures, living a finite life, so first of all, we need to ensure we have a finite amount of hypotheses so we can analyze them and tell whether a statement follows from them or not, in a finite number of steps. So that's the first thing we want: start from a finite set of statements to get to a conclusion in a finite number of steps. Now, what else do we want? We want to make sure that when we ensure the hypotheses are true, then so are the conclusions, in other words, the conclusion needs to be true when the hypotheses are true. It cannot be the case that we have true hypotheses and get false conclusions.

2.1.1 Logical implication

We have discussed some ideas about what we want to ensure a statement follows from other statements:

1. We start from a finite set of hypotheses and check if given another statement, this follows from the hypotheses.
2. If the hypotheses are true, then the conclusion must be true, that is, we cannot deduce false stuff from truths.

But how do we develop all these ideas in a proper mathematical language? We'll make use of a special type of functions called *valuations* to define the *logical implication*². Intuitively, a valuation is an interpretation of a statement, and it tells whether given a statement α , it's true or not. That is, $v(\alpha) = 1$ means α is true and $v(\alpha) = 0$ means α is false under the valuation v .³

Now we can write "If the hypotheses are true, then the conclusion must be true" in terms of valuations as it follows:

Definition 2.1 (Logical implication). *Let Γ be a set of statements and let φ be a statement. We write $\Gamma \models \varphi$ if $(\forall \psi \in \Gamma, v(\psi) = 1) \implies v(\varphi) = 1$ for a given valuation v and we say that Γ logically implies φ or φ is a logical consequence of Γ .*

The above definition asserts that any valuation that makes all the statements of Γ true, makes φ true, or, equivalently: there's no valuation for which φ is false but the statements of Γ are true. That's basically how we rigorously define reasoning, or inferring, so an inference rule will be any logically valid reasoning, that is, a set of hypotheses and a thesis that satisfies the definition.

In particular, when Γ is an empty set, we say φ is a *tautology* –a statement that's always true–.

²Sometimes called *tautological implication*.

³A valuation is a rigorous way to say "row of a truth table"!

There are several useful known inference rules, like, for example, *modus ponens* that says β follows from $\alpha \rightarrow \beta$ and α . In terms of our definition, we write $\alpha \rightarrow \beta, \alpha \models \beta^4$. This means that, if $\alpha \rightarrow \beta, \alpha$ are true, then so is β .

2.1.2 The *Reductio ad Absurdum* principle

There's a special rule of inference that we care about, and it's the following one: $\perp \models \beta$. Here \perp is a statement that's always under any valuation: a contradiction. That rule of inference is called *ex falso quodlibet*, and it states that given any contradiction, we can conclude any statement β , even if it's false or absurd. In other words, the system we're working on becomes *inconsistent* and that inconsistency makes everything trivial: we cannot tell whether a statement proven is true or false. This is why mathematicians hate contradictions! Contradictions are dangerous!⁵

There's a fundamental proof method loved by every mathematician:

Theorem 2.1 (*Reductio ad Absurdum*). *Let Γ be a set of formulas⁶ and φ a statement. Then $\Gamma \models \varphi$ iff⁷ $\Gamma, \neg\varphi \models \perp$ ⁸*

What does this principle say? Well, it says: " φ follows from Γ if and only if assuming the statements of Γ along with $\neg\varphi$, we get to a contradiction". Here, $\Gamma \cup \{\neg\varphi\}$ means that the set $\Gamma \cup \{\neg\varphi\}$ is inconsistent. In other words, there's no valuation that makes every statement of that set true at the same time.

This is the same principle that Euclid used to prove the infinitude of primes, or the method used to prove that $\sqrt{2}$ is irrational in a more general way, considering a set of statements that might or might not be empty. I will not prove it here because it's outside the objectives of this essay, however, we'll assume it's true by the *LaTeX Theorem* that says: "If it's in LaTeX then it must be true!".

This theorem is pretty useful because if we want to prove φ follows from Γ , it's enough to show that assuming Γ and $\neg\varphi$ leads to a contradiction – and we already said why do we hate them! – and vice versa: if assuming Γ and $\neg\varphi$ leads to a contradiction, then φ follows from Γ . However, what does it have to do with automated theorem proving? Well, first of all, we need to develop the concept of conjunctive normal forms and then a particular inference rule called *resolution*. There's when *Reductio ad Absurdum* becomes pretty useful.

3 Conjunctive normal forms (CNF's)

Given any set Π of connectives, it's said to be **complete** when you can define any other connective using the connectives of Π . An example of a complete set of connectives is: $\Pi = \{\neg, \wedge, \vee\}$, this means that you can express any other

⁴Properly speaking, we should write $\{\alpha \rightarrow \beta, \alpha\} \models \beta$ but we'll omit the brackets.

⁵There are ways to deal with contradictions without caring about *ex falso quodlibet* with the so-called *paraconsistent logics*. I recommend you to look up for them, they're crazy.

⁶Another way to say "statements" or "propositions"

⁷"iff" is an abbreviation of "if and only if".

⁸Here, we should write $\Gamma \cup \{\neg\varphi\}$ if we want to be rigorous.

connective in terms of those three, for example: $p \rightarrow q$ is equivalent to $\neg p \vee q$ ⁹. As a consequence of the completeness of that set, we have a pretty useful theorem, but first, we need to state the following definition:

Definition 3.1. *A conjunctive normal form (CNF) is a proposition of the form: $C_1 \wedge C_2 \wedge \dots \wedge C_n$ where each C_j is a disjunction of atomic variables or negations of atomic variables. Each C_j is called a clause.*

The following are examples of conjunctive normal forms:

1. $(A \vee \neg B) \wedge (C \vee B)$
2. $B \vee C$
3. A

Where A, B, C, \dots, Z represent the atomic variables¹⁰

Why are the last two CNF's tho? Well, $B \vee C$ is a clause and it's part of a conjunction of only one conjunct. Similarly, A is part of a clause with only one disjunct, and that clause is part of a conjunct of only one conjunct. The first example clearly follows the definition, so it doesn't need more explanation.

Now we can state the following:

Theorem 3.1. *For each statement φ there exists a CNF φ' such that φ and φ' are equivalent.*

The way we find the CNF given any formula is to use logical equivalences that involve only the connectives of our given set: the negation, conjunction or, disjunction and applying De'Morgan's Laws.

The proof of this theorem is related to the fact that $\{\neg, \wedge, \vee\}$ is complete. However, we only care about the fact that there's a CNF for any statement we want, for example: $p \rightarrow q$ is equivalent to $\neg p \vee q$.

4 Resolution

The last logical tool we'll develop before going to the automatic theorem provers, is an inference rule that operates over CNF's. The *Resolution method*. I'll also explain how it can be used to prove that a statement follows logically from a set.

4.1 What's it and why do we care?

You start with a CNF. imagine that a statement letter A occurs in a clause C_j of the given CNF and $\neg A$ in another clause C_k . Then, a nonempty disjunction is obtained by eliminating A from C_j and $\neg A$ from C_k and taking the disjunction of the remaining atomic variables. This new disjunction is said to be obtained *by resolution on A*. For example, consider the following CNF:

⁹You can check using a truth table. It's an exercise to the reader.

¹⁰Also called *statement letters or literals*.

$$\varphi = (A \vee \neg C \vee B) \wedge (\neg A \vee D \vee \neg B) \wedge (C \vee D \vee A)$$

We can apply resolution on C of the first and third conjuncts and we get $(A \vee \neg B \vee D)$. We can do this with all the conjuncts iterating the procedure. At some point, the process must stop. The result of cojoining all the disjunctions obtained to the original CNF will be denoted by $\mathcal{R}(\varphi)$ for a given CNF φ . For the example given:

$$\mathcal{R}(\varphi) = (A \vee \neg C \vee B) \wedge (\neg A \vee D \vee \neg B) \wedge (C \vee D \vee A) \wedge (\neg C \vee \neg B \vee D) \wedge (D \vee \neg B \vee C) \wedge (A \vee \neg B \vee D) \wedge (D \vee \neg B)$$

From now on, we'll not see $\mathcal{R}(\varphi)$ again but we'll keep the resolution rule stated as follows:

Definition 4.1 (Resolution).

$$\text{RES} \frac{A_1 \vee \dots \vee A_n \vee p \quad B_1 \vee \dots \vee B_m \vee \neg p}{A_1 \vee \dots \vee A_n \vee B_1 \vee \dots \vee B_m}$$

This notation means that given any two CNF's, say $A_1 \vee \dots \vee A_n \vee p$ and $B_1 \vee \dots \vee B_m \vee \neg p$ where each A_j, B_m and p are statement letters¹¹, we can conclude $A_1 \vee \dots \vee A_n \vee B_1 \vee \dots \vee B_m$. In terms of **Definition 2.1**, we write: $A_1 \vee \dots \vee A_n \vee p; B_1 \vee \dots \vee B_m \vee \neg p \models A_1 \vee \dots \vee A_n \vee B_1 \vee \dots \vee B_m$ ¹².

Remark. When an empty clause is produced by resolution, we say we have a contradiction and we write \perp .

4.2 Proofs using resolution refutation

Imagine we want to show $\Gamma \models \varphi$. Recalling the *Reductio ad Absurdum* principle, it suffices to show that $\Gamma, \neg\varphi \models \perp$. We can achieve this by applying resolution: if we get an empty clause at the end, we must conclude $\Gamma \models \varphi$. Here are a couple of examples of proofs using resolution, one of them using *Reductio ad Absurdum*:

Example: Let $\Gamma = \{P \wedge Q \rightarrow R, S \wedge T \rightarrow Q, S, T, P\}$. Prove that $\Gamma \models R$.

According to the *Reductio ad Absurdum* principle, the thing we have to do is to show that $\Gamma, \neg R \models \perp$. If we use resolution, we need to consider as hypotheses: $\{P \wedge Q \rightarrow R, S \wedge T \rightarrow Q, S, T, P\} \cup \{\neg R\}$. If we get an empty clause, we're done.

To apply resolution, we need to convert all the hypotheses into CNF. As an exercise, the reader will verify that the following CNF's are equivalent to the propositions we had earlier: $\{\neg P \vee \neg Q \vee R, \neg S \vee \neg T \vee Q, S, T, P\} \cup \{\neg R\}$ [HINT: Truth tables]

Now resolution can be done as shown in the proof tree below:

¹¹Before we used A, \dots, Z to denote statement letters, but p, q, \dots, z are also valid notations. We can also use a subindex.

¹²To see this is an inference rule, assume that the hypotheses are true but the conclusion false. In order for that to happen, we would need each C_j, D_k to be false but that would contradict the fact that the hypotheses are true, and that's a problem!

From these two methods, we usually will use resolution and the *Reductio ad Absurdum* principle. This technique receives the name of: **refutation by resolution** or simply “refutation” when there is no ambiguity.

Notice that we’ve worked on examples where the CNF’s obtained from the sets Γ are simply disjuncts. When we’re dealing with a CNF involving more than 1 conjunct of disjunctions, that is, our CNF’s are in the form $C_1 \wedge \dots \wedge C_n$ where each C_j is a clause, we can apply the following theorem to break it into a set containing C_1, C_2, \dots, C_n as its elements:

Theorem 4.1. *Let $C_1 \wedge \dots \wedge C_n$ be a CNF where each C_j is a clause and let φ be a statement. Then $C_1 \wedge \dots \wedge C_n \models \varphi$ iff $C_1, C_2, \dots, C_n \models \varphi$.*

This follows straightforward from the definition of logical implication and the definition of the truth table for \wedge , though it’s pretty useful when dealing with a CNF that needs to be separated into its conjuncts to apply resolution.

We’re almost ready to explore how this can be made into a computer program, but before i’ll mention another thing we can do using resolution.

4.3 Consistency proofs

We’ve shown how to prove $\Gamma \models \varphi$ using resolution, but we can do something else too: given any set of statements, we can check if it’s *consistent*, in other words, if it has no contradictions on it. How do we do that? Well, there’s an algorithmic process for it too:¹⁶.

- We want to check if a set Σ of statements is consistent.
 1. Convert all the elements of Σ to CNF
 2. Negate all the statements on the set
 3. Apply resolution iteratively
 4. If you get \perp , the set is consistent¹⁷, otherwise, it’s not consistent.

A set of formulas –also called a theory– is said to be *valid* if every valuation satisfies the given set.

These concepts might be useful when dealing with a bunch of axioms to see if they’re consistent, or if a bunch of premises are consistent. However, now we’re ready to explore how to code an automatic theorem prover.

¹⁶A **theory** is a set of statements. Resolution can be used to check if a theory is consistent or not.

¹⁷Another way of saying *consistent* is *satisfiable*, which means that there is at least a valuation that makes all the statements of the set true at the same time.

4.4 Resolution and programming: A computer doing proofs

We've discussed how to do some proof using resolution, and i gave a few examples of it. We also noticed that the process can be written in steps, like a recipe. In other words, there's an algorithm to do proofs using resolution, and if there's an algorithm that's simple like the given ones, we can go to our computer and write some code to automate the task, because, as we saw, it's easy but might be long and tedious. In other words, we're lazy so we're gonna develop more tools to do those things that are not worth our time or patience. For this purpose, we'll use python, but first, we need to define all the steps that the program will have to make in order to do a proof.

For the sake of simplicity, we will make a basic automatic theorem prover using resolution refutation that only accepts clauses in CNF, but the reader could try to do a more complex theorem prover that normalizes each statement given to check if another statement follows from them. However, the steps the program will follow are the next:

(The knowledge base or hypotheses)

- We want to prove $KB \models \alpha$ where KB is called the “knowledge base”¹⁸ and α is a query, the statement we want to prove.
 1. Ask for the cardinality of KB
 2. Ask for each one of the elements of KB (We'll only accept statements of the form: $A, \neg A, A \vee B, \neg A \vee \neg B, \neg A \vee B$)
 3. Ask for the query (The statement we want to prove. It must have the form of the above statements)
 4. Attach $\neg\alpha$ to a set KB' where this set is defined as $KB' := KB \cup \{\neg\alpha\}$
 5. Perform resolution
 6. Check for the output to see if it's \perp or no
 7. If it's \perp , conclude $KB \models \alpha$, otherwise, conclude $KB \not\models \alpha$
 8. Print the result

We will code several functions in order to get our ATP¹⁹.

¹⁸This is used in the context of AI.

¹⁹Automatic Theorem Prover..

```

def main():
    kb = []
    num_statements = int(input("Enter the number of
        statements in the Knowledge Base (KB): "))

    for i in range(num_statements):
        statement = input(f"Enter statement {i+1} (in CNF, e
            .g., 'A OR ~B OR C'): ")
        clauses = statement.split(' OR ')
        kb.append(set(clauses))

    # Ensure the query is a single literal or its negation
    while True:
        query = input("Enter the statement to prove (a
            single literal, e.g., 'A' or '~B'): ").strip()
        if query and (query.isalpha() or (query.startswith
            ('~') and query[1:].isalpha())):
            break
        print("Invalid input. Please enter a single literal
            or its negation (e.g., 'A' or '~B').")

    if resolution(kb, query):
        print("The statement follows from the KB.")
    else:
        print("The statement does not follow from the KB.")

```

This is the main function of our ATP. Let's analyze what it does:

1. KB is our knowledge base
2. num_statements is the cardinality of KB
3. The *for* loop will ask you for a statement until you match the cardinality of KB. That is, if $|KB| = 2$, the loop will ask you for 2 statements. **They must be in CNF.** When you give all the statements of KB, the loop splits the CNF into the literals (or negations of literals) to attach them to KB.
4. For simplicity, we will only accept literals or negations of literals as valid inputs, the *while* loop checks if the input is alphanumeric. It also checks if it starts with a negation or not. If it is alphanumeric, breaks the loop, otherwise, throws an error message.
5. If the query is alphanumeric, then we'll call the **resolution** function that will perform the procedure and check if the given query follows from KB.

Before defining the **resolution()** function, we'll define a couple functions that will be used to negate a literal and to perform resolution given two clauses.

This function here negates any given literal:

```
def negate(literal):  
  
    if literal.startswith('~'):  
        return literal[1:]  
    else:  
        return '~' + literal
```

This function takes a literal: if it already has a negation, we return the literal without the negation. This is like applying the double negation laws. If the literal doesn't have a negation, we add it up. Then, we return the literal.

We will also define the following function to resolve two given clauses:

```
def resolve(c1, c2):  
  
    resolvents = set()  
    for literal in c1:  
        if negate(literal) in c2:  
            # Create a new clause by combining c1 and c2 and  
            # removing the complementary literals  
            new_clause = (c1 | c2) - {literal, negate(  
                literal)}  
            resolvents.add(frozenset(new_clause))  
    return resolvents
```

this function will take two clauses. The loop will iterate over the literals of the first clause C_1 and will check if the negation of any of those literals, say p_i is in the clause C_2 . If this happens, we will combine C_1 and C_2 and remove the complementary²⁰ literals. Basically what we do in **Definition 4.1**. Then, we add this new clause to the *resolvents* set and return it to use it in our **resolution()** function. That function will perform resolution to check if the query follows from the KB.

²⁰A literal and its negation are called complementary.

This is our desired function! Now, how does it works in first place? Let me explain.

```
def resolution(kb, query):
    clauses = set()
    for clause in kb:
        clauses.add(frozenset(clause))

    negated_query = {negate(query)}
    clauses.add(frozenset(negated_query))

    while True:
        new = set()

        pairs = [(c1, c2) for c1 in clauses for c2 in
                 clauses if c1 != c2]
        for (c1, c2) in pairs:
            resolvents = resolve(c1, c2)
            if frozenset() in resolvents:
                # If the empty clause is derived, the query
                # is proven
                return True
            new.update(resolvents)

        if new.issubset(clauses):
            return False

        clauses.update(new)
```

This function takes as parameters the KB given when the **main()** function is executed, and the query. Then we add all the clauses in KB to the set **clauses** and we add the negated query too²¹. The next thing we do, is to generate all the possible pairs of clauses to be resolved. That's what we do in the *while* loop when we create the set of pairs.

the *for* loop iterates over all the possible pairs to apply the function **resolve()** we already defined. We do this to all the pairs! Now, **frozenset()** is an empty set that will represent our empty clause \perp . If there's an empty clause, then we return **True**. This output is interpreted in the **main()** function, and when **True** is returned, it outputs $KB \models \alpha$ where α is the query.

The set *new* is used to check whether we can keep doing the resolution process after we checked all the pairs we had. That set contains all the resolvents²² and we're checking if $new \subset clauses$. if this happens, it means no more clauses can be derived because no new information can be obtained and \perp was no derived in first place, so the function outputs a **False** that **main()** interprets as $KB \not\models \alpha$. At the end we just update the set of clauses to keep iterating.

²¹As we do in refutation!

²²What we obtained by applying resolution.

The full code looks like this:

```
def negate(literal):
    if literal.startswith('~'):
        return literal[1:]
    else:
        return '~' + literal

def resolve(c1, c2):
    resolvents = set()
    for literal in c1:
        if negate(literal) in c2:
            new_clause = (c1 | c2) - {literal, negate(literal)}
            resolvents.add(frozenset(new_clause))
    return resolvents

def resolution(kb, query):
    clauses = set()
    for clause in kb:
        clauses.add(frozenset(clause))

    negated_query = {negate(query)}
    clauses.add(frozenset(negated_query))

    while True:
        new = set()
        pairs = [(c1, c2) for c1 in clauses for c2 in clauses if c1 != c2]
        for (c1, c2) in pairs:
            resolvents = resolve(c1, c2)
            if frozenset() in resolvents:
                return True
            new.update(resolvents)

        if new.issubset(clauses):
            return False
        clauses.update(new)

def main():
    kb = []
    num_statements = int(input("Enter the number of statements in the
    Knowledge Base (KB): "))

    for i in range(num_statements):
        statement = input(f"Enter statement {i+1} (in CNF, e.g., 'A OR ~B OR
        C'): ")
        clauses = statement.split(' OR ')
        kb.append(set(clauses))

    while True:
        query = input("Enter the statement to prove (a single literal, e.g.,
        'A' or '~B'): ").strip()
        if query and (query.isalpha() or (query.startswith('~') and query
        [1:].isalpha())):
            break
        print("Invalid input. Please enter a single literal or its negation (
        e.g., 'A' or '~B').")

    if resolution(kb, query):
        print("The statement follows from the KB.")
    else:
        print("The statement does not follow from the KB.")

if __name__ == "__main__":
    main()
```

Sorry for the Bible-like styled font size but otherwise it would have not fit on the screen.

Before we move on to the last chapter, i want run some examples using above's code to check if some of the following famous inference rules are indeed valid reasonings:

Modus Ponens

$$\text{MP} \frac{p \rightarrow q \quad p}{q}$$

In first place, we need to convert all into CNF. In this case, we just need to normalize $p \rightarrow q$. Remember it's equivalent to $\neg p \vee q$, so the inputs we'll give to the ATP are $\neg p \vee q, p$ like this:


```

C:\WINDOWS\system32\cmd. x + v
C:\Users\4sole\Desktop>python Prover.py
Enter the number of statements in the Knowledge Base (KB): 2
Enter statement 1 (in CNF, e.g., 'A OR ~B OR C'): ~p OR q
Enter statement 2 (in CNF, e.g., 'A OR ~B OR C'): p
Enter the statement to prove (a single literal, e.g., 'A' or '~B'): q
The statement follows from the KB.
C:\Users\4sole\Desktop>

```

Figure 1: Automated proof of *Modus Ponens*

Here, $KB = \{\neg p \vee q, p\}$ and we wanted to show $KB \models q$. Indeed it does, and as an exercise, you can verify it doing resolution by yourself²³.

Now let's try with this one. **Modus Tollendo Tollens**

$$\text{MT} \frac{p \rightarrow q \quad \neg q}{\neg p}$$


```

C:\WINDOWS\system32\cmd. x + v
C:\Users\4sole\Desktop>python Prover.py
Enter the number of statements in the Knowledge Base (KB): 2
Enter statement 1 (in CNF, e.g., 'A OR ~B OR C'): ~p OR q
Enter statement 2 (in CNF, e.g., 'A OR ~B OR C'): ~q
Enter the statement to prove (a single literal, e.g., 'A' or '~B'): ~p
The statement follows from the KB.
C:\Users\4sole\Desktop>

```

Figure 2: Automated proof of *Modus Tollendo Tollens*

Checking this inference rule is pretty straightforward too when we use resolution, taking $KB = \{\neg p \vee q, p\}$ to show $KB \models \neg p$, however the computer

²³Test your understanding!

can do it faster than us!²⁴ The following example is immediate, just “cancelling out” $\neg p$ and p to get q , however, let’s see what does the computer says!

Disjunctive Syllogism

$$\text{DS } \frac{p \vee q \quad \neg p}{q}$$


```

C:\WINDOWS\system32\cmd. x + v
C:\Users\4sole\Desktop>python Prover.py
Enter the number of statements in the Knowledge Base (KB): 2
Enter statement 1 (in CNF, e.g., 'A OR ~B OR C'): p OR q
Enter statement 2 (in CNF, e.g., 'A OR ~B OR C'): ~p
Enter the statement to prove (a single literal, e.g., 'A' or '~B'): q
The statement follows from the KB.

C:\Users\4sole\Desktop>

```

Figure 3: Automated proof of *Disjunctive Syllogism*

Now let’s check if this one is an inference rule or not. Firstly, we will do it using our ATP, and then, we’ll do it using resolution by-hand, and we’ll compare. We’ll also use the definition of logical implication. I’m sure your favorite method will be the automated proof because of how easy it is.

$$\frac{A \vee B \quad \neg A \vee C}{C}$$

Method 1: ATP


```

C:\WINDOWS\system32\cmd. x + v
C:\Users\4sole\Desktop>python Prover.py
Enter the number of statements in the Knowledge Base (KB): 2
Enter statement 1 (in CNF, e.g., 'A OR ~B OR C'): A OR B
Enter statement 2 (in CNF, e.g., 'A OR ~B OR C'): ~A OR C
Enter the statement to prove (a single literal, e.g., 'A' or '~B'): C
The statement does not follow from the KB.

C:\Users\4sole\Desktop>

```

Figure 4: The ATP’s answer

²⁴Also doing it by hand is pretty tedious.

The ATP says $KB \not\models C$. This is a fact, now, the program does not say *why* it doesn't follow, so let's analyze it using resolution refutation and the definition of logical implication:

Method 2: Resolution

Assuming $\neg C$ we have:

$$\text{RES} \frac{\text{RES} \frac{A \vee B \quad \neg A \vee C}{B \vee C}}{B} \quad \neg C$$

And we did not get a contradiction, so according to what we said in previous chapters, we cannot conclude $KB \models C$ because of the *Reductio ad Absurdum* principle. Let's do it with the last method.

Method 3: Logical Implication

We want to show $KB \models C$ where $KB = \{A \vee B, \neg A \vee C\}$, i.e., $A \vee B, \neg A \vee C \models C$. Following **Definition 2.1**, this means that every valuation v that makes $A \vee B$ and $\neg A \vee C$ true at the same time, makes C true too. We can do the truth tables for the statements of KB and C and compare the rows where they're true, and you'll find out that there's an assignment of truth values that makes the statements of KB true but C false. This assignment is $v(A) = v(C) = 0$ and $v(B) = 1$. In other words, $KB \not\models C$ because of this assignment.

This was the longer explanation, and trying to find the particular assignment can be tedious, however, it is still useful to understand *why* $KB \not\models C$. But if your purpose is to check if a reasoning is valid only, then using an ATP will make your life easier²⁵.

4.5 BONUS: A Theorem prover using DNA molecules???

Our ATP has an enormous disadvantage. If n represents the number of literals you have to perform resolution on, there are $n!$ different ways to pick an arrangement and do the resolution process, and that is what the computer will do. This means that, having 10 literals, the ATP will perform resolution in $10! = 3,628,800$ different ways. Now, aren't computers powerful enough to do that kind of computations? Well, it depends. First, we need to understand what's *complexity* and what is the execution time of a program.

4.6 Some Computation-Related Concepts

When we write a program, especially if we are going to use it several times, we want it to execute in the shortest time possible. The time it takes to execute a program, in our case, will depend on the entries, the "size" of the entries (the number of literals in this case). The time will then be modeled by a

²⁵You can even add a function to tell you why tho it would be a bit more complicated, but possible.

function that depends on the number of entries, say n . Let's call this function $T(n)$. Given that the time will depend not only on the entries but also on the computer we're working on, and other factors, we will not specify units most of the time, however, we can give an expression such that for large values of n , approximates $T(n)$ using the "Big-O" notation. More precisely, given constants n_0, c , we say that $T(n)$ is $O(f(n))$ if $T(n) \leq cf(n)$ for $n \geq n_0$. In other words, as n becomes larger, $f(n)$ becomes an upper bound of the time it takes the program to execute.

For the case of the resolution refutation algorithm, the complexity, meaning the number of entries, grows, and so does the time it takes to execute. Using Stirling formulas we get that for $n!$ entries, our asymptotic approximation will be $O(n^n)$, that is, for a large n , the execution time grows exponentially as the complexity of the proof becomes larger. In other words, if you want your computer to explode, just give it a lot of statements as input.

Is there a solution to this tho? What can we do? Fortunately, in computing, there's a concept called *parallelism*. Basically, it means that we can execute several processes at the same time: they're parallel and this has an advantage: executing several processes at the same time takes less time but you also get a more efficient way to run programs. Supercomputers are examples of applied parallelism. There is another problem though: it is vulgarly expensive and polluting to maintain a computer like that.

All this opens the question: Is there a way to perform resolution in a faster but cheaper and less energy/time consuming than a conventional computer? Well, the answer is YES. But, how?

Well, you probably are gonna say i am crazy but, let me tell you that DNA molecules can perform resolution in less time than a regular computer because of the parallelism. I know, right now you are thinking "How the hell can DNA molecules do a mathematical proof?". It's simpler than it seems, but we will need some biology concepts first!²⁶

²⁶Check In-Hee Lee et al in the bibliography. They did this amazing research:)

4.7 Some Biology Stuff

DNA are the molecules that store the genetic information that contains basically all information about you! Tells us how tall we can be, the skin color, eye color and even diseases.²⁷

Figure 5: Mr.DNA

Just listen to Mr.DNA talk, he explains pretty well what DNA is. Highly educative and fun content over there.

DNA means deoxyribonucleic acid. It's made out of tiny pieces called nucleotides, where each nucleotide is made out of: a sugar molecule, in this case, deoxyribose; a phosphate group and a nitrogenous base: adenine (A), guanine (G), thymine (T), cytosine (C) and uracil (U). We will focus on the first four.

Figure 6: Nucleotide

That's what a nucleotide looks like. We have a sugar molecule²⁸, the phosphate group and the nitrogenous base. Now, something that's important is the position of some carbon atoms inside the nucleotide, because they will be used

²⁷No, it cannot tell if you're gonna become rich tho.

²⁸deoxyribose is a special case of a pentose.

to determine two fundamental concepts: *the lagging chain and the leader chain* and the concept of *complementary chain*.

Figure 7: Nucleotide with labeled carbon

This image shows the positions of some important carbon atoms: positions 5', 3' and 1'. We only care about the first two because those are the places where all nucleotides join together by hydrogen bonds to make the famous double helix we know and adore. The following image shows the way it's done:

Figure 8: Example of a DNA chain

We can notice two fundamental things from this diagram of a double helix:

1. The nucleotides join to form bonds at the carbon atoms 5' and 3'
2. One chain has direction 5'-3'. This one is called **leader chain**
3. The other one has direction 3'-5'. This one is the **lagging chain**
4. The nitrogenous bases bound in pairs using nitrogen bonds: A is to T and G is to C. This will always be like that, otherwise we would have a mutation.

The last three observations are **really** important, and the fourth is particularly important to understand what a complementary chain is. Imagine we have the following nitrogenous base chain: AGCTG. Then the Watson-Crick complementary sequence or simply complementary sequence²⁹, will be TCGAC according to the observation (4).

With that in mind, we can now encode atoms using sequences of nitrogenous bases of the same length to encode a literal, whereas the complementary sequence will represent its negation. Here's an example:

Figure 9: Encoding the literal A and its negation using DNA sequences

Here, the sequence ACGTTAGA represents the literal A . Therefore, the complementary sequence is TGCAATCT. The arrow in the image indicates the 5'-3' direction. The literals will be represented by a leader chain, so the complementary change has direction 3'-5'. We just need to flip it up and we have TCTAACGT like Figure 9.

4.7.1 Some biotechnology

We already know how to code a literal using a DNA sequence, but how do we perform resolution? First of all, we only know how to encode literals using DNA, so any possible proposition must be broken into their literals first: we know that any given formula α has a CNF that's equivalent to it. Given α , assume α' is the corresponding CNF. Then $\alpha := C_1 \wedge \dots \wedge C_n$ where each C_j here represents a clause, that is, each C_j is a disjunction of literals or negations of literals. Using **Theorem 4.1**, we can break α' into its clauses. So if KB contained α , now it contains all the clauses of α' . Each clause is a disjunction that can be represented by a concatenation of DNA sequences. So for example, if we have $\neg Q \vee \neg P \vee R$, we can represent it by concatenating the sequences of $\neg Q$, $\neg P$ and R as follows:

²⁹Or chain.

Figure 10: Concatenation of the sequences of $\neg Q$, $\neg P$ and R

Here, we have a single sequence made out of simpler sequences concatenated together.

Now that we know how to encode any statement using DNA sequences, we can mix all these DNA molecules in order to get the analogous to our KB set. What's next? We need a way to perform resolution by first understanding what hybridization is: When we take two single-stranded DNA sequences and join them into a double-stranded DNA sequence, this process is called *hybridization* and we achieve this by joining together a literal and its negation through an enzyme called ligase that catalyzes the formation of phospho-diester bonds that join the nucleotides of the single-stranded sequences to form a double helix.

Every time a literal encoded by a sequence ligates to another one, the rest remain unchanged. A literal and its negation form an empty clause, then two sequences matched together –a literal and its negation– make an empty clause too. Otherwise, if there are molecules having a single-stranded sequence, they were not ligated to a complementary sequence. Notice how this is pretty similar to what we did when we were describing the procedure to decide whether a proof was found or not.

The next step after hybridization would be amplifying the ligation products, that is: creating copies of the specific sequences we want. In our case, we will only amplify the ligation products that can be a valid proof (those ones that do not have single-stranded sequences). This can be done using a technique called PCR (polymerase chain reaction). The polymerase is an enzyme used in the replication process of the DNA in our cells, and we systematically repeat an artificial process to amplify specific regions of the sequence, those ones that can be useful for us.

Figure 11: The processes described above: encoding, concatenating and applying the hybridization and ligation.

Figure 12: How a PCR is done

The primers shown in the image are DNA fragments designed to indicate polymerase which region of the sequence they are going to amplify: the region between the primers is the one that will be amplified. This is how we guarantee we only amplify the desired region of a DNA sequence. In our case, the goal sequences will be the primers.

The last step would be checking if we found a valid proof or not. To separate the molecules, there's a method called gel electrophoresis:

Figure 13: Gel Electrophoresis

The DNA sequences that were amplified are put in gel and an electric current goes through the gel causing the DNA molecules to move: the longer ones will move to the negative direction given it's harder for them to move, while the shorter DNA sequences will move to the positive electrode.

The article i'm referencing to for writing about this, performed resolution refutation with DNA molecules to prove that $P \wedge Q \rightarrow R, S \wedge T \rightarrow Q, S, T, P \models R$ assuming $\neg R$. Belo's diagram shows how to perform resolution to prove it.

Figure 14: Proof: R follows from the premises.

Here, *nil* represents the empty clause. It's the same thing as \perp . Given that $KB, \neg R \models \perp$, they concluded $KB \models R$.

clause	sequence
$\neg Q \vee \neg P \vee R$	CGTACGTACGCTGAA CTGCCTTGCGTTGAC TGC GTTCATTGTATG
$Q \vee \neg T \vee \neg S$	TTCAGCGTACGTACG TCAATTTGCGTCAAT TGGTCGCTACTGCTT
S	AAGCAGTAGCGACCA
T	ATTGACGCAAATTGA
P	GTCAACGCAAGGCAG
$\neg R$	CATACAATGAACGCA

Figure 15: Sequences for linear implementation (Resolution refutation) in order of from 5' to 3'.

To do it using DNA molecules, they used the following sequences:
This is a resume of the process followed:

Figure 16: Steps to do resolution with DNA molecules

To get an empty clause, all of the 5 variables must be resolved. Every time we resolve a variable, a double-stranded region with 15 bp³⁰ is produced. Therefore, we can expect a 75 bp band will appear³¹ at some point. The electrophoretogram in Figure 17 shows an empty clause was produced. Thus, a proof for the given problem was found, i.e., $KB \models R$.

³⁰base pairs

³¹15 times 5 = 75

Figure 17: Electrophoretogram of the PCR product in the linear implementation. Lane 1: PCR products with S and $\neg R$ as primers. Lane 2: PCR products with $\neg S$ and R as primers. Lane M is a size marker.

This is a resume on how we can perform resolution using DNA molecules, however, the researchers added this important discussion on the experimental results they got: *There are some points to be considered to expand this implementation. First of all, we should rearrange variables in each clause to make an empty clause form a linear double-stranded molecule. This requirement poses a limitation on the type of clauses we can use. That is, some kind of clauses do not make a linear double-stranded molecule no matter how we rearrange the variables. Also, it is impossible to know in advance which sequence to use as a primer. And there are possibilities of false positive.*

In other words, this method still needs to be improved to achieve a result that's as good as a computer program. However, this represents a big advance in nonconventional computation.

5 Conclusions

We learned a little bit more about how mathematicians think and operate, what's the purpose of mathematical logic and how we can make a computer do proofs. We also explored an unconventional use of DNA molecules to perform the resolution refutation as the computer did, however both in a pretty simple way, especially the python program. The latter can be extended and improved by adding functions to convert any given formula to its corresponding CNF and then perform the resolution, also without limiting the query to a literal or negations of literals. You can even extend it to first-order logic, for example, though you would need to consider quantifiers, the predicate symbols, and so on. However, the purpose was to show how we can translate *a part* of the job mathematicians do to an algorithm so a computer can perform it. These Automated Theorem Provers can be pretty useful but they're still quite simple compared to something a human mathematician has and a computer could just envy³²: creativity and abstraction capacities. A machine can perform algorithmic tasks faster than we can, or even with more precision, however, they cannot –at least yet– do what a mathematician does in terms of pretty abstract and complicated proofs. That's why computers have not solved millenium problems or fail sometimes to do some simple reasoning. They also lack *intuition*, this sort of ability to get knowledge apparently out of nowhere instantly. Intuition plays a fundamental role in mathematics but also has a lot to do with creativity –and can help to reason–. These qualities a human has but a computer doesn't, are what keep mathematicians working on every day on different problems, so even if they –ironically– created the tools to perform the tasks that give them a purpose –proving mathematical facts– automatically, by now they're more a help than a threat. I don't think computers will ever achieve the power of the human, but it can emulate a lot of things and can be pretty useful, and as we saw, their development depends a lot on mathematicians' work, so at least they will keep their jobs when AI grows a lot! haha

Something that is also worth talking about is the scope of a concept when you mix when you do interdisciplinary work: we started doing resolution purely by mathematical means that were later translated into a computer program. However, this was not too optimal and we found a method to do it using DNA molecules, which is pretty unexpected but shows how we can find new ways to improve if we think a little bit outside the box: at first glance, who would have ever thought that DNA molecules could be able to do this?

Sometimes, knowledge is not found by opening new doors, but by putting a door in there so you can use it.

Hope you all, guys, find this useful and/or interesting. Thanks for reading!

³²If they had feelings of course.

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